

ICAENS 2022 PROGRAM

Opening Ceramony - 10 MARCH 2022 09:00-11:00

SPEAKERS

1	Josep M. Guerrero (Keynote Speaker)
2	Mohammad S. Obaidat (Keynote Speaker)
3	Amirrudin Kamsin (Keynote Speaker)
4	Muhammad Sultan (Keynote Speaker)
5	Roohollah Bagherzadeh (Keynote Speaker)

Session 1.1		10 MARCH 2022 11:00-12:00	
TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Ses Yalıtım Malzemesi Olarak Kullanılan Melamin Süngerin Hidrofobik Özelliğinin İncelenmesi	Merve Okutan and Filiz Boran	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 102
Ultrases destekli hidrotermal yöntemle sentezlenen ZrO ₂ nanoparçacıkların yapısal özellikleri üzerine ısı işlem türünün etkisi	Filiz Boran and Merve Okutan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 127
Bacteriocin production potential of cheese-borne Staphylococcus hominis	Sümeyye Akbulut, Elanur Tuysuz, Ahmet Adıgüzel and Hakan Özkan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 109
Farklı Sıcaklık ve Sürelerde Yapılan Islatma İşleminin Baklagillerin Toplam Fenolik Miktarı ve Antioksidan Aktivitesine Etkisi	Ebrar Altıkardeş and Nihal Güzel	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 550
Selenoid System-Based Recovery System Design and Analysis for Medium-Altitude Rockets	Mustafa Furkan Tekle and Murat Bakirci	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 593
Accretive growth kinematics with elastic curves	Gül Tuğ	Turkey	Submission 179
Removal of Dissolved Organic Matter in Drinking Water Using Active Microorganisms (EM)	Zehra Gülten Yalçın, Mustafa Dağ and Ercan Aydoğmuş	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 16
Computer Aided Deep Learning Based Assessment of Stroke From Brain Radiological CT Images	Ali Berkan Ural	Turkey	Submission 18
Effects of particle size on transportation of Sporosarcina pasteurii through porous media	Kağan Eryürük	Turkey	Submission 21
Cu ₂ O ve Al ₂ O ₃ Nanopartiküllerin Motor Performans ve Emisyonlara Etkisinin İncelenmesi	Gürsel Çınar and Oğuzhan Akyüz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 24

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High Performance Electrochemical Double Layer Capacitors Derived from Red Pepper Pulp-Based Microporous Activated Carbons	I. Isil Gurten Inal and Filiz Koyuncu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 27
Yüzey İyileştirme Yöntemlerinde Bor Elementinin Kullanımı	Recep Demirsöz, Oğuzhan Çakır and Mehmet Tayyip Özdemir	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 31
MacWilliams Identities For The Linear Codes Over $Z_4+uZ_4+vZ_4$	Basri Çalışkan	Turkey	Submission 32
Effect of Hydrazine Modification on Paper Pulp Production from Wheat Straw with Soda Method	Ayhan Tozluoğlu, Ahmet Tutuş, Selva Sertkaya, Ufuk Kılılı and Recai Arslan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 34
Süperiletken kabloların AA kayıplarını ölçmek için kullanılan yöntemlerin karşılaştırılması ve termal bir yöntem	Rıfki Terzioğlu and Türker Fedai Çavuş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 35
Sezgisel Bulanık TOPSIS Yöntemi Kullanılarak Bir Cam İşleme İşletmesinde Makine Seçimi	Buse Duygu Dağıdır and Barış Özkan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 36
Studying Wetting Kinetics of Sn-0.7Cu Binary Lead-Free Solder Alloys	Awam Mahmood Rahmadan Bakr, Serkan Oguz and Ahmet Mustafa Erer	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 39
Optimization of Parameters Affecting Anti-Icing Performance on Wing Leading Edge of Aircraft	Hayati Kadir Pazarlıoğlu, Ahmet Ümit Tepe and Kamil Arslan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 4
Çöp döngüsünün etkili bileşeni: poşet çay atıkları ve Ni ²⁺ adsorpsiyonu	Hakan Çelebi, Tolga Bahadır, İsmail Şimşek, Şevket Tulun and Melayib Bilgin	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 43
Optimization of Parameters Affecting Drying of Noodles by Taguchi Method	Rana Başataç, Zehra Gülten Yalçın, Mustafa Dağ and Ercan Aydoğmuş	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 45

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Kemik Rejenerasyonu için Farklı Gözenek Oranlarındaki Kafes Tabanlı Gözenekli Yapının Geçirgenlik Performansının Değerlendirilmesi	Derya Karaman and Hücet Kahramanzade	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 46
Estimating the Amount of CH ₄ and CO ₂ Emissions from Solid Wastes by Using the LandGEM Mathematical Model	Nesli Aydın	Turkey	Submission 48
Çok Kriterli Karar Verme Yöntemi İle Elektrikli Araç Şarj İstasyonu Yer Seçimi	Hilal Yurt and Barış Özkan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 49
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Strophoidal Surfaces	Erhan Güler and Ömer Kişi	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 54
Epirochoidal Hypersurfaces in 4-Space	Erhan Güler and Ömer Kişi	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 55
Plazma Elektrolitik Parlatma Yöntemi Üzerine Bir Derleme	Mustafa Enes Yazıcı and Hasan Demirtas	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 56
On Lacunary Convergent Complex Uncertain Triple Sequences Determined by Orlicz Function	Ömer Kişi and Erhan Güler	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 57
I-Statistical Convergent Sequence Spaces of Fuzzy Star-Shaped Numbers	Ömer Kişi and Erhan Güler	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 58
The Effect of Layer Thickness on the Mechanical Properties of 3D-Printed Parts by Finite Element Analysis Method	Meltem Eryıldız	Turkey	Submission 60

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TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Farklı Tuz Konsantrasyonlarında Semiz Otu (Portulaca oleracea) ve Kamışsı Yumak (Festuca arundinacea) Bitkileri Uygulanarak Tuzlu Toprakların Fitoremediasyon Yöntemiyle İyileştirilmesi	Hasan ER, Semih ELİBOL	Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission-5
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Optimizing Sustainable Development Goals through digitalized CE in Food Supply Chain	Batin Latif Aylak	Turkey	Submission 71
Investigating the Effect of Light Stress on Cell Size, Number, Protein, and Chlorophyll Concentration of Chlamydomonas reinhardtii ami-RNA Mutant and Wild Type	Tuba Sevgi	Turkey	Submission 76
SiO ₂ coated carbon interlayer for Li-S batteries	Meltem Yanılmaz	Turkey	Submission 78
Determination of the Antimicrobial, Anti-Quorum Sensing and Anti-Biofilm Potential of Bacteria Extracts Isolated from Fish	Belgin Erdem, Dilek Yalçın and İlkay Açıkgöz Erkaya	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 83
Using Nature in Architecture A perspective from Antoni Gaudi	Seyda Emekci	Turkey	Submission 86
Influence of HCl activation on the Ammonia Adsorption Properties of Natural Clinoptilolite	Orkun Ergürhan and Burcu Erdoğan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 93
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Geology and Geochemistry of Copper Mineralization of Volcanic Rocks Due to Quartz Veins in Western Part of Almus (TOKAT-TURKEY)	Cihan Yalçın, Mustafa Kumral, Mustafa Kaya and Muhittin Karaman	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 9
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Investigation by Confocal Raman Spectroscopy of Basic Volcanic Rocks of Yüksekova Complex (Elazığ, Turkey)	Cedide Kaymak and Melek Ural	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 115
Investigation of Thermophysical Properties of Polyester Composites Produced with Synthesized MSG and Nano-Alumina	Hakan Şahal and Ercan Aydoğmuş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 117
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Üç Pimli Prepreg Kompozitlerde Çeşitli Pim Konumlandırmalarının Araştırılması	Mehmet Çağrı Tüzemen	Turkey	Submission 133
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Türkiye'de aşılama oranı ile COVID-19 pandemisi arasındaki ilişkinin matematiksel bir analizi	Orhan Dalkılıç and Naime Demirtas	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 150
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İki Biarum Taksonunun Mikromorfolojik Özelliklerinin İstatistiksel Karşılaştırılması	Ali Özdemir and Canan Özdemir	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 160
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Randomized Decomposition Methods in Multi-objective Evolutionary Algorithm based on Decomposition for Many-objective Optimization Problems	Tolga Altinoz	Turkey	Submission 162
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Morphology investigation of porous carbon nanofibers	Göktuğ Cihanbeyoğlu and Meltem Yanılmaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 187
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Türkiye'de aşılama oranı ile COVID-19 pandemisi arasındaki ilişkinin matematiksel bir analizi	Orhan Dalkılıç and Naime Demirtas	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 150
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Mode-Matching Analysis of Rigid Pipe with Partial Lining	Hülya Öztürk	Turkey	Submission 180
The Polynomial Sequence Generalizing the Integer Sequence which Enumerates the Number of Subsets of the Set [n] Including No Two Consecutive Even Integers	Barış Arslan and Kemal Uslu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 183
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Green Synthesis of Zinc Nano Fertilizer and Its Effect on Plant Growth	Havva Kaya and Semra Kilic	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 203
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Gamma and Neutron Shielding Estimation for Hastelloy N	Hakan Us	Turkey	Submission 217
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A Relative Assessment of Genetic Algorithm and Binary Particle Swarm Optimization Algorithm for Maximizing the Annual Profit of an Indian Offshore Wind Farm	Prasun Bhattacharjee, Rabin K. Jana and Somenath Bhattacharya	India, India, India	Submission 242
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Cardiac Arrhythmy Classifier	Cansu Ecemiş, Neslihan Avcu and Zekeriya Sarı	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 233
Application Of Chicken Swarm Optimization To Travelling Salesman Problem And A Reviewing Of Similar Studies	Süleyman Özer, Adil Baykasoglu and Özcan Kilincci	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 360
Position-based New Mathematical Model for Type II Assembly Line Balancing Problem with Sequence-dependent Setup Time	Ahad Furugi	Turkey	Submission 533
Metanolün Elektrokimyasal Yükseltgenmesi İçin Pt katalizör Destek Malzemesi Olarak Tiyofen Kullanımı	Sadaf Adhami and Evrin Hür	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 354

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PDOA/TWR Based Real-Time Localization System For Smart Factories.	Burak Yaşar Çoldaş and Adnan Kaya	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 374
Application of Different Image Processing Techniques on ASTER for Exploration of Chromite Deposits On Yellice Village-Sivas and Its Surroundings	Oktay Canbaz	Turkey	Submission 426
Your Digital Twin: Metahuman	Kemal Gökhan Nalbant and Şevval Uyanık	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 130
Elektro-Pnömatik Bir Valfin Akış Karakteristiğinin İncelenmesi ve İyileştirilmesi	Lütfü Tutar and Elif Erzan TopÇu	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 564
Ni-B-CeO ₂ Kompozit Akımsız Kaplamanın Mekanik ve Tribolojik Özelliklerine Isıl İşlem ve Yükün Etkisi	Deniz Gültekin, Erhan Duru and Hatem Akbulut	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 572
ADR'li Tankerlerde Kullanılan Kaynaklı ve Kaynaksız Çeliklerin Mekanik Özelliklerinin Karşılaştırılması	Furkan Emin Buğan, Emin Emre GÖktepe, Tufan Altıparmak and Erhan Duru	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 555
The Effect of Cylindrical Twisting Process on Material in Transition Cone Manufacturing Used in Aluminum Fuel Tankers	Furkan Salman, Emin Emre Göktepe and Erhan Duru	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 240
Ni-BW Kaplamalarında W Konsantrasyonunun Sertlik ve Aşınma Özelliklerine Etkisi	Erhan Duru, Abdullah Öztürk, Mehmet Uysal, Hatem Akbulut and Serdar Aslan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 605
Covid-19 Sürecinin Su Ayak İzine Etkisinin Değerlendirilmesi	Sevde Üstün Odabaşı	Turkey	Submission 137

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Linear Codes Over A Special Ring	Neslihan Aytaç and Murat Güzeltepe	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 449
Avionics and Recovery System Conceptual Design for a Subsonic Rocket	Muhammed Mirac Ozer and Murat Bakirci	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 591
Immobilization of Amylases via Adsorption on Agar-Coated Magnetic Nanoparticles	Nihal Yılmaz and Suzan Biran Ay	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 534
Effect of Ethylene Glycol and Glycerol Concentrations on Properties of Rye-Based Films	Nurcennet Ertürk and Suzan Biran Ay	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 544
Analyzing of Cyber-Security Concepts on Twitter	Nazmiye ElİğÜzel and Lana Manla Ali	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 114
Determination of Concentration and Bulk Precipitation Fluxes of Polychlorinated Biphenyls (PCBs) at Different Surfaces and Depths with Passive Snow Sampler in Erzurum, an Important Winter Tourism Center	Cihan Paloluoğlu	Turkey	Submission 546
Broadband Low Reflection Surfaces with Silicon Nanotubes Square Arrays with Quantum Dot Layer	Turgut Tut	Turkey	Submission 469
Baskı Devre Kart Malzemesi Seçiminde Analitik Hiyerarşi Süreci Yöntemi	Ahmet Cihan	Turkey	Submission 484
Farklı Renklerdeki Cam Lifi Takviyeli Betonlarda (GRC), Xenon Arc Yaşlandırmasının Renk Değişimine Etkisi	Sefa Guntepe, Serkan Subasi, Muhammed Marasli and Volkan Ozdal	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 579

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TITLE	Author Names	COUNTRY	SUBMISSION ID
Polifenol Oksidaz Enziminin <i>Lepista personata</i> Mantarından Saflaştırılması ve Karakterizasyonu	Elif Kaya and Ayşe Türkhan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 618
Development of Low Cost Water Purification Technology For Rural Community	Kemal Ahmed, Amare Adugna and Zehra YİĞİT Avdan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 470
FASULYE GENOTİPLERİNDE TUZ ve KURAKLIK STRESLERİ ALTINDA VPE GEN AİLESİNİN GENOM ÇAPINDA ANALİZİ ve KARAKTERİZASYONU	Ahmed Sidar Aygören, Selman Muslu, Murat İsiyel, Burak Muhammed Öner, Ayşe Gül Kasapoğlu, Recep Aydın, Esra Yaprak, Sümeyra Uçar, Emre İlhan and Murat Aydın	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 565
Fasulye bitkisinde phospholipase D gen ailesinin tuz ve kuraklık stresi altında genom çaplı karakterizasyonu	Murat İsiyel, Burak Muhammed Öner, Esra Yaprak, Sümeyra Uçar, Ayşe Gül Kasapoğlu, Ahmed Sidar Aygören, Selman Muslu, Recep Aydın, Emre İlhan and Murat Aydın	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 567
PvTLP genlerinin genom çaplı tespit ve karakterizasyonu	Ayşe Gül Kasapoğlu, Ahmed Sidar Aygören, Selman Muslu, Burak Muhammed Öner, Murat İsiyel, Esra Yaprak, Sümeyra Uçar, Büşra Uzun, Recep Aydın, Emre İlhan and Murat Aydın	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 568
Nor-wogonin'in İnsan Rahim Ağzı Kanseri Hücreleri Üzerine Antikanser ve Apoptotik Etkilerinin Araştırılması	Ahmet Karakuş and Sevgi Ünal Karakuş	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 599
EFFECT OF WALNUT SEED SKIN AGAINST MAIN ORGAN DAMAGE CAUSED BY HYPERLIPIDEMIA	Esra Palabiyik, Seda Aşkin and Hakan Aşkin	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 273
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Lucas Sayı Dizisinin Entropi Yönünden İncelenmesi	Bünyamin Şahin and İhsan Tuğal	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 13
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Improving the Interlaminar Bonding Performance of Additively Manufactured Continuous Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastic Composites Using an Infrared Heat Source	Altuğ Uşun, Bahri Barış Vatandaş and Recep Gümrük	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 430
Fast, One-pot and Environmentally Friendly A New Method for Synthesis of Nickel Oxide (NiO) Nanoparticles	İbrahim Hakkı Karakaş	Turkey	Submission 569
Termik Santral Kaynaklı Çevre Kirliliğini Önlemek İçin Baca Gazı Arıtma Teknolojisi:Örnek Çalışma Seyitömer Termik Santrali Uygulaması	Şeyma Kaçmaz and Havva Demirpolat	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 244
Dual-Band Microstrip Patch Antenna Design for Wi-Fi Applications	Sezer Kucukcan and Adnan Kaya	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 319
Design and Interpretation of Microstrip Patch Antenna Operating at 2.4GHz for Wireless WI-FI Application	Ekrem Akar and Gokcen Demirbas	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 314
High-Gain Circularly-Polarized Square Patch UHF RFID Reader Antenna Design for Smart Factory Applications	Gulbahar Guven, Ismail Akdag and Cem Gocen	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 305
High-Gain Rectangular Patch Microstrip Antenna for IEEE 802.11 b/g Applications	Hilal Kurt and Adnan Kaya	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 331
A Dual-Band Antenna Design for 2.4 and 5 GHz Wi-Fi Applications	Yasar Kaplan and Cem Gocen	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 309
Covid-19 Kısıtlamaları Süresince İç Anadolu Bölgesi'nde Hava Kirlenmelerindeki Değişimin İncelenmesi	Göktuğ Türkyılmaz and Bahtiyar Efe	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 259

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Asymmetrical Coplanar Vivaldi Antenna Design	Recep Bař and Ahmet Kızılay	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 478
Fluvalinatın Van Balığı Böbređi Üzerine Histopatolojik Etkileri	Ayşe Nur Kıraçcakalı, Burcu Ergöz, Elif Kaval Ođuz and Ahmet Regaib Ođuz	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 341
GELİŐTİRİLMİŐ PARÇACIK SÜRÜ OPTİMİZASYON ALGORİTMASI İLE DA-DA ALÇALTICI TİP DÖNÜŐTÜRÜCÜNÜN Pİ KATSAYILARININ OPTİMİZASYONU	Ersagun Kürőat Yaylacı, Ahmet Erdem Yılmaz and Hatice Nur Özdeő	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 176
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Kare desenli Alüminyum Sođurucu Yüzeye Sahip bir Güneő Hava Kollektörünün HAD Analizi	Sharif Eyyublu and Mahmut S Buker	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 621
Türkiye’de trafik sigorta primlerinin Haris őahin Algoritması ile tahmini	Mehmet Fatih Tefek and Muhammed Arslan	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 594
Makine Öğrenmesi ile Hedefe Yönelik Nanoterapötiklerin Üretim Parametrelerinin Optimizasyonu	Naim Karasekreter, őeyda Gündüz, Sadık Kađa and Süleyman Yaman	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 620
Termal Bariyer Kaplamaların Biriktirilmesinde Atmosferik Plazma Sprey Prosesi Parametrelerinin Optimizasyonu	Savaő Öztürk	Turkey	Submission 561
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ok Ynl Dvme İřleminin AA5083 Alminyum Alařımının Mekanik zellikleri zerindeki Etkisi	Erkin Akdođan and Mehmet Őahbaz	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 560
TOPOLOGICAL FEATURES OF FRACTAL CUBIC NETWORK GRAPHS	Burhan Seluk and Ayře Nur Altıntař Tankl	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 164
Dıřtan Dıřli Pompalarda Farklı Sıvı Elastisite Modulnn Hacimsel Debi zerindeki Etkilerinin İncelenmesi	same Ali Usca and Mahir Uzun	Turkey, Turkey	Submission 538
The Effect of PEEK-Rod Fixation Systems on Finite Element Lumbar Spine Model	Saliha Zeyneb Akıncı, Derya Karabulut, Hasan Kemal Srmen, Onur Yaman, Yunus Ziya Arslan	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Mail Submission 9
Green synthesis and characterization of silver nanoparticles using leaves of Quercus pubescens	Muhammet Kamil Kerim and Recep Tas	Turkey, Turkey, Turkey	Submission 554
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Metasurface Based Reflection Type Linear Polarization Conversion for X Band Applications	Gkhan ztrk	Turkey	Submission 628
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